

Search strategy of the systematic review on tilting table tests of masonry assemblies

Alejandro Jiménez Rios¹

Lara Smit²

Claire Ristow³

Onni Heino⁴

Quentin Pierson⁵

Kathy Cheean⁶

¹Department of Build Environment, Oslo Metropolitan University, 0130 Oslo, Norway

²Department of Applied Physics, Hogeschool van Amsterdam, 1091 GC Amsterdam, Netherlands

³Department of Mechanical Engineering and Engineering Mechanics, Michigan Technological University, 49931 Houghton MI, United States

⁴Department of Industrial Engineering and Management, Metropolia University of Applied Sciences, 02610 Espoo, Finland

⁵Department of Data Intelligence, ISEP Paris, 75006 Paris, France

⁶Department of Data Science and Artificial Intelligence, ESIEE Paris, 93160 Noisy-le-Grand, France

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	I
List of tables	II
List of figures	III
1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review Literature Search (PRISMA-S)	1
1.1 Introduction	1
1.2 Search strategy	1
References	3
Annex A	4

List of tables

Table 1. Information sources and methods..... 1
Table 2. Search strategies..... 1
Table 3. Peer review..... 2
Table 4. Managing records 2
Table 5. History of changes..... 4

List of figures

No table of figures entries found.

1 Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review Literature Search (PRISMA-S)

1.1 Introduction

Systematic reviews quality heavily relies in the search strategy implemented for the information retrieval process. Nevertheless, search strategies are commonly not adequately reported. This document presents the search strategy adopted to perform the systematic review of the “Tilting Table Tests of Masonry Assemblies” European Project Semester¹ and it is based on the PRISMA-S [1] checklist.

1.2 Search strategy

The recommended items to address in a search strategy according to the PRISMA-S checklist are presented in Table 1, Table 2, Table 3 and Table 4. This search strategy has been developed and documented to ensure transparency of the systematic review and facilitate its reproducibility.

Table 1. Information sources and methods.

Database name:	The following electronic databases were searched: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus: Scopus delivers the broadest coverage of any interdisciplinary abstract and citation database, covering 240 disciplines. • Web of science: It is the world’s most powerful research engine. A multidisciplinary platform with over 1.7 billion searchable cited references. • IEEE Xplore: It is a research database for discovery and access to journal articles, conference proceedings, technical standards, and related materials on computer science, electrical engineering and electronics, and allied fields. • Oria: OsloMet Library database.
Multi-database searching:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engineering Village: Provides access to search across 12 databases in the engineering fields.
Study registries:	Not applicable.
Online resources and browsing:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google scholar: It allows keywords searching like those in Scopus and Web of science. A python script was developed to efficiently extract the reference data provided by the search. • Wiley Online Library: It offers a portfolio of over 8 million articles from 1,600 journals.
Citation searching:	Backs and forwards citation will not be necessary and are outside of the scope of this review. This is due to timeline constraint and the low level of complexity required.
Contacts:	Due to the duration of this systematic review, no authors will be contacted. If a piece of research is determined to need more information, information that can only be found via contacting the author, we will remove it from consideration for inclusion on this review.
Other methods:	Not applicable.

Table 2. Search strategies.

Full search strategy:	Two initial keywords and similar terms of interest (namely: masonry and tilting table) were used to create the following search queries: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus: ALL (masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test*")) AND PUBYEAR > 2009 AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE , "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "ar") OR LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE , "cp")) • Web of science: masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test*") • IEEE Xplore: masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test") • Engineering Village: (((masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test"))) WN KY) AND ((({ja} OR {ca}) WN DT) AND ({english} WN LA)))
------------------------------	--

¹ <http://europeanprojectsemester.eu/>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Google scholar: masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test") • Wiley Online Library: masonr* AND ("tilting table" OR "tilting test")
Limits and restrictions:	Apart from the keyword queries we will include several limits on our searches in our review. Firstly, we will only be considering conference papers, journals, and articles all of which must be peer reviewed. To be included the research will need to be written in English or have a published English translation version. Also, we will only include research from 2010 or newer. All these filters were added in addition to the queries listed above to achieve the results that are stated below.
Search filters:	None.
Prior work:	None, we are creating a new systematic search strategy for this review.
Updates:	Our research team will not receive updates for changes in the research included. This is because this review will be conducted over a brief period, and it is unlikely any updates will occur.
Dates of searchers:	The search was conducted on 13/09/2023.

Table 3. Peer review.

Peer review:	The search strategy document will be made available online along with the systematic review protocol in the OSF website. Both documents are available to receive open peer reviews under the Resources tab of the project Registry website DOI: https://osf.io/ezrkt [2]
---------------------	---

Table 4. Managing records.

Total records:	A total of 506 works were found: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scopus: 23 • Web of science: 8 • Google Scholar: 7 • IEEE Xplore: 1 • Wiley Online Library: 1 • Engineering Village: 18 • Oria: 448
Deduplication:	Our research team will be using the software Mendeley to manage our references. This software will assist us in the collection and storage of data found in our systematic review. Mendeley will be utilized to spot and remove any duplicate work.

References

1. Rethlefsen, M.L., et al., *PRISMA-S: an extension to the PRISMA Statement for Reporting Literature Searches in Systematic Reviews*. *Systematic Reviews*, 2021. **10**(1): p. 39 DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13643-020-01542-z>.
2. Jiménez Rios, A., et al., *Systematic Literature Review on Tilting Table Tests of Masonry Assemblies*. 2023, OSF. <https://osf.io/ezrkt>.

Annex A

Table 5. History of changes.

Version	Publication date	Change
1.0	18/10/2023	Initial version.

